

Ground State Link to Free Particle $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$?

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It is well known that a quantum free particle has a $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta p = \hbar/p$ such that for the nonrelativistic case: $\Delta x / \Delta t = 1/2m \cdot 1/\Delta x$. Here we note that a very similar result holds for the ground state of the harmonic oscillator $W = C \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2)$ if one uses the standard deviation for $W(x)W(x)$, i.e. $\Delta x / \Delta t$ is proportional to $1/2m \cdot 1/\Delta x$. The same result holds for the infinite well potential as we show. We argue that there seems to be a link between a $\Delta x / \Delta t$ of a quantum ground state and that of a free particle. To find a general relation, we consider the Schrodinger bound equation: $-1/2m d^2W/dx^2 + V(x)W = E_n W$ and consider a x_0 such that $V(x_0)=0$ (i.e. the free particle case). Then one may approximate $W(x)$ as a single hump peaked at x_0 . If one approximates this with a $\sin(kx)$ one may see that $1/k$ is proportional to a base length and that one has $1/2m L^2 = E_n$, from which one finds the relationship: $\Delta x / \Delta t = 1/2m \cdot 1/\Delta x$. One does not necessarily need to use a $\sin(kx)$ function, but can use a Gaussian or other functions to obtain a similar result.

As a result, we suggest that there is a link between a free particle $\Delta x / \Delta t$ and that of a ground state.

Free Particle Case

A quantum free particle has a:

$\Delta t = \hbar / E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar / p$ ((1)) We set $\hbar=1$.

Thus, $\Delta x / \Delta t = 1/2m \cdot 1/\Delta x$ ((2)) for the nonrelativistic case.

It would at first seem that ((2)) would have nothing to do with the ground state of a bound single quantum particle.

Quantum Oscillator

The ground state of a quantum oscillator is described by:

$E_0 = .5 \hbar \omega$ ((3a))

$W(x) = C \exp(- (.5m\omega/2\hbar) x^2)$ so that $W^2 = C^2 \exp(- (m\omega/2\hbar)x^2)$ ((3b))

If one uses the standard deviation as Δx , then

Standard deviation = $\sqrt{2\hbar/m\omega}$ and $\Delta t = \hbar / (.5 \hbar \omega)$ ((4))

Then $\Delta x / \Delta t$ proportional to $1/2m \cdot 1/\Delta x$ ((5))

Infinite Well Potential

For an infinite well potential;

$$E \text{ ground state} = \frac{1}{2}m \left(\frac{3.14 \hbar}{L} \right)^2 \text{ and } \Delta x = L, \Delta t = \hbar / E \quad ((6))$$

$$\Delta x / \Delta t \text{ proportional to } \frac{1}{2}m \frac{1}{\Delta x} \quad ((7))$$

General Case

We now try to develop a general case by considering the bound state Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((8))$$

If one considers a ground state to be a single humped wavefunction with a peak at x_0 , one may consider potential which has $V(x_0)=0$ which holds for the oscillator and infinite well potential.

Then:

$$-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \text{ at } x_0 = E_n \quad ((9))$$

Considering W as a single hump, it may be approximated by a $\sin(kx)$ where $\Delta x = L = 1/k$. This leads to;

$$\frac{1}{2}m \frac{1}{L^2} = E_n \text{ or } \frac{1}{2}m \frac{1}{L} = E_n L = \Delta x / \Delta t \quad ((10))$$

Thus, one obtains the general result for $\hbar=1$ of $\Delta x / \Delta t = \frac{1}{2}m \frac{1}{\Delta x}$.

This only holds for the sin wave, but other single hump wavefunctions, like a Gaussian, seem to give similar results. Thus, there seems to be a connection between $\Delta x / \Delta t$ for a free particle and the ground state.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that for a quantum free particle one has: $\Delta x / \Delta t = \frac{1}{2}m \frac{1}{\Delta x}$ where $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ (here $\hbar=1$). We note that a very similar result holds for the ground state of both the harmonic oscillator and the infinite well potential. We then try to generalize to the case for which the ground state wavefunction is a single hump and $V(x_0)=0$, where $W(x_0)$ is the hump peak. We then find $\Delta x / \Delta t = \frac{1}{2}m \frac{1}{\Delta x}$ in general.